

Life on the edge: senior women in science.

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Abstract

The lack of movement of women into higher-level teaching or executive positions in Australia's universities is consistent with patterns reported elsewhere throughout the developed world. Is this a result of choice, or is it the result of an inhibiting environment? Does the lack of women in these higher echelons matter, and will it threaten improvements for women in lower positions? Can reasonable action be taken to redress the imbalance of women in senior positions? Does the mid-career academic woman have particular issues?

The proportion of women in higher education institutions varies with discipline, but science, in particular engineering, has the lowest representation. A review of women in science at nine universities in Australia shows that women form a very small proportion of staff at senior lecturer and above, regardless of the type of university (new, medium or long-established). At the smaller campuses, low numbers of total staff mean that women in science are in single figures or absent.

Feedback is presented from a survey of senior women. These women attributed the low number of women in higher positions to few women having the required qualifications—a strong research profile—not the size of the available pool. This is generally due to a lack of time to devote to research activity. Women commonly have heavy family responsibilities, and take on a disproportionate collegiate burden. The lack of the establishment and maintenance of international links due to career interruptions, poor mobility, and lack of disposable income, is a major impediment to progress. Practical support, such as access to sabbatical leave, was considered vital, while mentoring (if done well) and informal networks were considered useful by many. The majority agreed that there was an inhibiting male culture prevalent in universities, in common with the rest of society, making it especially hard for women to gain ground. Few women considered that conditions will change in the future without a change in this culture, especially given the increasingly unattractive academic lifestyle.

Keywords: senior women, science, research, universities, male culture.

Background

Recent studies have clearly demonstrated that women do not persist into mid to upper career positions in Australia's universities (Jones et al. 1999, Probert, 2005 among others). This situation is similar in other countries, such as the United Kingdom. It is particularly evident in the sciences, as illustrated by the proportions of women to men of all academics, of senior academics, and of senior science academics at a range of universities in Australia (Figure 1). The proportion of women to men above senior lecturer is around 20 per cent for all disciplines, but is only 10 per cent in the sciences.

Figure 1: The ratio of female to male academics (non-executive) at a range of major, medium, and small regional universities in Australia. Ratios of female to male science staff obtained by the author from web site staff lists, and total staff data from the Department of Dept of Education, Science and Training (2003).

Lack of progression of women into higher levels at universities has been attributed to two main factors: an inhibitory and 'unhelpful' climate (Sullivan 1999; Handlesman et al 2005), and to difficulties related to the balance between family and workplace commitments (Gardner 1998; Probert 2005: 51-2). This is simplistic, as rarely do either of these factors operate alone.

Before discussing the position of women in employment in academic science, the basic criteria for success in that environment need to be summarised. Firstly a PhD is usually mandatory. The rather surprising (to me) statistic that many women still manage to get positions at universities in Australia, even at associate lecturer, without a PhD (Probert, 2005: 55) is not common in the sciences. Secondly, international publications, a 'strong research record', and consequent international reputation, are prerequisites for promotion to senior positions. This approach has been strongly endorsed in the new Research Quality Framework

being proposed in Australia. Roles in teaching and administration are not regarded particularly highly in upper-level promotions criteria. This is only modified by consideration of performance 'relative to opportunity' in some research grant and promotions applications. 'Relative to opportunity' is, however, commonly undefined.

Aspects of the work environment and opportunity that might reduce a woman's ability to compete in academia have been the topic of much action over recent years. Bursaries have been available for staff (including women) to upgrade their qualifications. This varies with institution and perceived need. Transition universities, such as the ex-Colleges of Advanced Education, were particularly active in this regard, but the practice has declined. 'New-start' bursaries have been instituted at several universities to assist young women with career interruptions to recommence their academic careers. Collegiate schemes, such as 'women in research' programs, are not uncommon (eg WomenResearch 21 at UNSW and a similar group at Central Queensland), while societies such as the Women in Science Enquiry Network (WISEnet) and the Australian Federation of University Women (AFUW) cut across universities. Formal mentoring schemes also exist to support staff. These options, together with equity representation on committees, and changes to promotions application processes, have gone a long way toward improving women's status at universities (Winchester et al 2005). The effectiveness of these actions has been less studied, and employment statistics suggest there may be some recalcitrant causes still unaddressed. If we are to have a healthy and sustainable society, we need to tap into the knowledge, talents, and skills of all of our population.

There is a three-tier university system in Australia: major, 'sandstone' universities which are the oldest, generally the largest, and capture the majority of research funding (a matter which they are keen to perpetuate); mid-range universities, established mostly in the 1970s, some now very large, but still substantially younger and with a few exceptions, less status-loaded than the 'sandstones'; and finally, the newer 'Dawkins' universities, younger than 20 years, formed largely from Colleges of Advanced Education (CAEs) and commonly based in regional or fringe-urban areas of the country. Expensive courses like medicine and engineering are rare at these latter universities, while agricultural and environmental science are common, in keeping with their locations. At present, all universities have access to research funding, which was not the case for the CAEs, which is a matter of some tension within the sector. Promotions criteria are relatively uniform across the sector.

The ratio of females to males in science faculties (not including nursing) at a selection of new universities (Ballarat, Charles Sturt, Murdoch–Peel campus, Southern Cross and Southern Queensland), two mid-range (James Cook and Wollongong), and two major (the Universities of Melbourne and New South Wales), shows that the situation differs little between university type (Figure 2). The sole exception was at senior lecturer level where the ratio of females to males was significantly higher ($F = 5.43$, $p = 0.045$) at the mid-range universities (63 per cent of senior lecturers are women, heavily affected by high numbers of female senior lecturers at Wollongong) than at both the other two (22 per cent women). The average at all surveyed universities at associate professor level was 20 per cent \pm 3 while at professor level was 7 per cent \pm 7.

Figure 2: The ratio of females to males grouped according to university type. Data obtained from published information available for each university on their web sites, and in some cases confirmed by phone calls to particular departments

In order to explore the causes of the low representation of women in science, and what instruments might be useful to improve their advancement, fifty-five senior women scientists (associate professor and above) from a range of universities were surveyed in this pilot study. ‘Science’ was defined to include:

- (i) the pure sciences (physics, chemistry, biology),
- (ii) environmental science (including environmental geography but not human or economic geography), and forestry,
- (iii) engineering, and
- (iv) the medical sciences.

Experimental psychologists were included, but women engaged in the sociology, say, of general practice medicine, were not. Nursing staff were not included. The validity of this definition of ‘scientist’ was commented on by some respondents, one engineer considering she was too ‘business’-oriented to be relevant. Having a base-line training in the sciences does not necessarily result in the practice of it. Unlike the ‘Athena Swan’ survey (Fox 2005) mathematics and computing were not included.

The women surveyed were identified by searching the web site of each university. This process was informative. The absolute number of senior women in science at some universities was extremely low, hence a higher number of universities in the ‘regional and young’ category (Table 1).

Table 1: Statistics from staff listings of senior women in science obtained from university web sites. These women were all invited to respond to the survey, with the exception of myself at Southern Cross University.

Classification	University	senior women in science or in executive with science background
major	UNSW	19
	Melbourne	19
mid-range	James Cook	9
	Wollongong	5
regional and young	Ballarat	1
	Charles Sturt	2
	Murdoch - Peel	0
	Southern Queensland	0
	Southern Cross	1

Thirty-six per cent (20) of the women surveyed responded. They are referred to in the following text by the letter 'R' and a number. This response rate was remarkably good given the short time-frame (two weeks) and the timing of the survey (coincident with the start of both school and university terms and the last stages of preparation for a major research grant application round in Australia).

The women were asked to respond to a range of issues raised in the literature, either by a combination of binary answer (yes/no), options ranking, or open-ended responses.

Results

Duration of service is normally positively correlated with the achievement of high-level positions (Probert 2005). The first question explored whether the low representation of women in the professoriate is largely a pipeline effect; few PhD students when the respondent completed her PhD, resulting in a small pool from which to now draw senior female staff members. Current statistics are that 44 per cent of PhD completions in the sciences (agricultural, environmental, natural, and physical) are women, such that women in these sciences are no longer considered an equity group (James et al 2004). In engineering, however, the percentage hovers around 18 per cent (Department of Education and Training, 2002). In 1999 there were more women than men in academia below the age of 49 (Jones et al 1999, and if these women are suitably qualified, many of them may move into more senior positions as older staff retire.

Responses were slightly ambivalent, with 55 per cent considering that there were factors other than duration of service contributing to the low numbers, and 40 per cent agreeing; the remainder abstained. Three people identified a loss of eligible women from the pool at lower

levels (women leaving academia to pursue other work options) as a problem. The working life of women and the outputs 'relative to opportunity' were highlighted by 44 per cent of respondents as more important than the duration of time in employment. A regional effect was mentioned by one respondent:

I suspect the correct answer is a partial yes [that is, it is a pipeline effect] but that it is much more complicated. Other likely influential factors include lower mobility and difficulty of finding positions for two professionals, especially in regional areas. I suspect that...a major factor for academic women is that they are likely to be partnered with academic or other ambitious professional men and that men prepared to be 'house husbands' are rare. (R14)

In some fields there were the same or even more female PhDs when the respondents were doing their PhDs than at present: 'there has been a high proportion of women PhDs graduating in my discipline [cell biology] for the past 12-15 years so this should have flowed through to the higher ranks more effectively than it has by now' (R12). One of the reasons given for the lack of retention was salary: 'The difference between academic salaries and those for medical specialists is already wide and increasing; it will become increasingly difficult to get anyone to take on an academic clinical post' (R3).

One respondent (R7) considered that softening the barrier between Associate Professor and Professor will improve the situation for both men and women, and two others noted that there had been a movement by women into 'leadership' (executive?) positions. These three responses were from staff at the same university where 'some excellent programs have been established...to encourage women to apply for promotion' (R13), although a staff member at the same university did not feel so positive: 'I've been an academic since 1989. I cannot say I see any changes whatsoever. Most junior appointments are men, and senior women remain as rare as hen's teeth' (R8). Several comments highlighted differences between disciplines and between universities: 'My perception is that things have got marginally better in terms of more women at level C/D but this may also be because I have moved from a research only school in a GO8 Uni to a teaching/research position at a regional uni' (R10).

As stated in the promotions policies of most universities, the main qualifications for promotion to the professoriate are an international reputation, underpinned by a strong research record as evidenced by publications, research grants, and research students. Respondents were asked what they thought were the major reasons for a lack of progression of women by ranking the following: (i) a lack of women with suitable qualifications, (ii) a lack of confidence by suitable women (despite a good success rate once they do apply), (iii) a lack of ability, or (iv) some other cause. Respondents soundly rejected the possibility that women lacked ability (scoring 4 on a 5 point scale), and evenly scored the other items at 1.65 (1 being 'most important'). Clarifying comments largely supported the point that well-qualified women will get promoted, but many lack the track record due to other commitments, some by choice, some 'forced' upon them. The former included:

Women tend to be far better 'corporate citizens' than their male counterparts. When volunteers are required for admin/committee/pastoral care roles in the University, women are more likely to agree to participate and contribute 'for the common good'. These activities come at the direct expense of their own research productivity and hence their track records in research (central to most promotion requirements) (R13).

Comment was made by several respondents about family responsibilities: 'it is very hard to travel interstate or overseas to develop research partnerships and do international grants. It's even hard to stay back after 5 for late meetings; men generally do not have these restrictions' (R1, corroborated by R20). These factors, even in well-qualified women, were thought to undermine women's confidence.

A few respondents mentioned procedural matters, one considering that equity in promotions still needs improvement (R16), and three expanding that Australian Research Council attempts at equity are so unclear as to be unhelpful and thus possibly ineffective. For example, although an international reputation and 'strong research record' are unarguably appropriate qualifications for promotion, it depends on how these things are measured. One respondent believed that 'strong research record' is largely about counting numbers of papers, not 'assessing the impact that research has achieved and measuring that'. She would 'rather publish fewer, meaty papers that...make a significant contribution to the field—and put them in high quality journals—than churn out piles of stuff to lard out my c.v. and impress referees of ARC grants...It's also men who are largely deciding what "strong record" actually means of course' (R8). 'Men are more inclined to play the game—where numbers count (perhaps the [academic] equivalent of mine is larger than yours?)' (R20). Perhaps Australia's new Research Quality Framework with its proposed emphasis on well-cited international-standard publications and collaborative research will help here, although networks of 'mates' who will cite your papers can heavily bias that system.

The lower publication rate of women reported by Tharenou (1994), Edwards et al (1998, p. 13) and Probert (2005, using within-discipline comparison), is an important matter when considering research success and promotion. The respondents were asked to explore this concept by ranking the options: (i) less time at work due to conflicting demands, (ii) less time after work (at night and weekends) due to family commitments, (iii) few PhD students to help write the papers, (iv) lack of publication experience, and/or (v) other reasons.

Options (i) and (ii)—less time—were overwhelmingly considered most critical to publication rate, scoring 1.4 and 1.5 on a 5 point scale. Time lost bearing a disproportionate load of administrative duties at work and fulfilling commitments at home was emphasised by half of the respondents as being a critical limiting factor to their ability to publish and hence win research grants.

Career interruptions (or a 'go slow'), and a lack of ability to take advantage of opportunities at an early stage in a career, were considered to have long-term repercussions (R12). The lack of ability to travel overseas on a regular basis was seen as a major factor reducing publication rate (R16). The importance of gaining large grants was noted by one respondent, who felt that '...Women don't seem to say how wonderful they are as easily as men do when going for grants' (R5). Confidence in 'getting out there' was seen as a critical attribute for publication and grant success (R9). A difference in approach to research and publications between women and men was commented on by several respondents: 'I do think that a different set of values about work—wanting to do things well and publish significant pieces of work or at least not producing endless bits of salami—could be a real difference in research values and ethics between men and women' (R8). One respondent commented that 'I [have] observed that my male colleagues do not take their responsibilities very seriously and certainly do not take more work than they can handle. I do and then I have no time to write publications' (R11).

This begs a question about research grants. Are women less successful? Do they apply in different ways for different sorts of grants? These statistics are difficult to obtain, certainly for a short-term study. Deane et al (1996: Figure 9) reported a vast differential between men and women in the applications for grants in the sciences in 1995; only five to fifteen per cent of applications came from women. In 2005, women reportedly had a similar success rate to men (23 and 28 per cent) in obtaining ARC Discovery grants (Commonwealth of Australia 2005). These statistics are not broken down into grant size or team membership. Eight of the respondents thought that women applied for smaller grants (due to caution, and/or lack of confidence or ambition), and were not often members of teams, both inside and outside the university: 'Men are more ambitious and have better links with industry to leverage the funding; also biases in the review process' (R1). However, six respondents firmly disagreed, two saying that in their experience women were particularly good in teams (R7, R18). The comment was made:

...most men are happy to play competitive games, so if they have been told they have to churn out heaps of papers, work in teams and do research by committee to get money, they will. But for women that strategy poses real problems. Most such teams will almost certainly be either all or predominantly male, meaning that the whole way in which the research is carried out will be driven by the way men tend to work together, which is (in my experience) often off-putting. Most groups of men indulge in competitive games and one-upmanship...Unless you happen to be in charge and can put a stop to it, it can be very tedious indeed...You only need one or two of those to make the team dysfunctional and to disenfranchise people. Other men are fine and hate that sort of stuff as well...I just don't think women, on average, work like that and I don't think pecking orders are as important. It's a real disadvantage when research teams are now flavour of the decade in research funding (R8).

The majority of respondents thought that women were just as energetic as men in applying for grants. Causative factors were similar to those for publication rates with 'lack of time' (2.3 on a 5 point scale) being most important.

There are mixed opinions about the existence of an inhibitory 'male culture' in universities. Overt discrimination on the basis of gender reportedly has been successfully tackled through employment and promotional policies (Winchester et al 2005, Probert 2005): a 'glass ceiling' does not exist. A 'chilly' campus climate, exclusion from departmental decision-making, slights about sexuality, and unconscious bias by males against females has been reported, however, to continue in many parts of the world (Handlesman et al 2005). Sixty five percent of respondents (question 5) agreed that, in their experience, an inhibitory male culture does exist. Only one respondent abstained. Three of those who answered 'yes' and the abstention, qualified their responses by saying they currently did not experience such a culture, but had in the past or in certain locations (R6, R9, R10 and R14). The 'male culture' was considered by some to be in common with conditions in the wider community (R4, R16) and in particular professional organizations (R3). Several felt that 'equal opportunity' policies had played a great part in improving the situation, but this had created a more difficult situation in that discrimination is no longer as overt. 'Only in parts and now mostly unconscious. More prevalent in older organisations and more prevalent 15 years ago' (R17). 'It's very subtle but the "handmaiden" concept is alive and well—also women who put themselves forward are seen as assertive and sometimes aggressive—men are seen as showing leadership skills...' (R15). Not all agreed, however, that the culture was hidden:

We are now left with the more intractable problems created by a workplace dominated by men, and yes I think the culture is there and it is overtly masculine. Getting on in academe revolves around accepting men's values, men's ways of doing things and so forth...(R8).

The majority of respondents (68 per cent) agreed that women spend more time engaged in non-research activities than their male counterparts. This was spread between administration and student support activities. It was suggested by some respondents that women had problems prioritising and refusing such tasks, and when they do take them on they are more conscientious than equivalent male staff. '[Heads of Schools] do not necessarily give appropriate career advice/mentoring and ensure that a balanced admin/research/teaching load is assigned' (R16). It was suggested by one respondent that engagement in these activities can be a 'cop out' (R9) to avoid more difficult research activity. The issue of being equity representative on selection committees was raised as a time-waster (R10, R17, R19).

One of the reasons for a diminution of women at higher echelons of universities could be a consequence of 'exhaustion'. This was a complaint of academic women in Probert (2005: 68). Respondents were asked to comment on this, and suggested reasons: (i) weariness from the effort required to maintain publication and research levels, (ii) adverse institutional culture, and (iii) unrelenting demands of the family (elder parents and difficult adolescents replacing young children). The majority of respondents agreed that there was an exhaustion factor in their lives, and they attributed it to option (i): 'It is the crisis of academia' (R4) and 'is felt by all staff' (R19). The addition of family responsibilities made the job particularly hard to sustain. One stated that she had refused higher responsibilities because of a desire to maintain some life outside the university (R9). A few respondents, however, commented that the university culture (option (ii)) creates some exhaustion issues: 'I have often agreed to participate in activities that drained my time and energy largely because I felt privileged to be invited to contribute. I think it is easier for women to allow themselves to be spread too thinly across competing demands' (R13); '...I have been upset on several occasions with the lack of credit given to women ie not giving them the opportunity to sit on committees and to make judgments in their field' (R12); and 'I get sick of the crap I hear of men who I know to be of mediocre talent that appear to get rewarded because they are good at promoting themselves' (R8).

The value and nature of mentoring and professional networks to assist women to develop their careers was explored (question 6). Several respondents had no experience of mentoring, but many felt it was very valuable. Although '...men cannot effectively mentor women as they do not understand the pressures' (R14), and one respondent reported an adverse experience with a male mentor (R11), others disagreed: 'some of my most helpful experiences have been from male mentors and role models' (R13). 'Stressing to women the importance of finding a mentor could be beneficial' (R6). The difficulty in obtaining a good female mentor has limited the use of mentor programs, even at mid-range universities (R10). The situation is demonstrably worse at smaller universities (Table 1). Several respondents resisted this approach, however, suggesting that it further 'promotes the "crutch" attitude that makes women feel less capable than men' (R4).

Programs instituted within universities gained considerable positive comment (nine respondents), although not all were aware of the existence of such programs in their universities. Four respondents did not think they were useful, two quite forcefully (R2, R18).

Indeed, some of these activities were thought to ‘take time away from core activities’ (R4). Two respondents were members of WISEnet, and one commented that it was ‘better for networking than heavy duty contacts’ (R19). None were members of AFUW. There appeared to be a general feeling that communication between women or peers in their discipline was valuable.

Other interventions were explored (Table 2). Basic, practical assistance was favoured, be it through administrative or other support for the writing of research grants and publications, the right to go on study leave or sabbatical, or the need for more within-faculty mentoring or support. Some of these mechanisms are already available in universities.

Table 2: Rating by respondents of interventions to assist female academics to progress to the professoriate and beyond. The score is on a scale of 1-5 with 1 most favourable.

Intervention	score
(i) practical support be provided for female academics for preparation of publications and research grants	1.9
(ii) study bursaries be provided for mid and late-career female academics	2.2
(iii) conference and meeting support for mid and late-career female academics	2.2
(iv) funding for attendance of affirmative action seminars	4.4
(v) research into issues related to the transition between senior lecturer associate professor to professor and the support required.	2.7

Strong reservation was expressed about such instruments, however, as they may appear to imply that ‘[women] need remedial help and/or that without special assistance we are not competitive in schemes open to both men and women’ (R13). ‘I would be too humiliated to accept money simply because I’m a woman and I suspect many other senior women might feel the same way’ (R8). The response to ‘further research’ was interestingly high, as some respondents commented that we know enough already: ‘If the source of disadvantage is male-based cultural values, then that’s what needs to be addressed’ (R8).

Reflections were sought on matters that were missed or that needed expansion. This elicited some of the most candid comments. The salary differential between academia and other employment options was mentioned by several as a major disincentive. Simple matters such as the hiring of a house cleaner or nanny were regarded as very important (R9) and low salaries make that particularly hard to do. Financial constraints in the university system encourage staff to engage in consultancies or confidential industry-funded research, but this is often given less credit than journal publications. Not having the power to use family funds for career advancement was mentioned.

One respondent commented that women tend to be more ‘risk averse’ than men, adding that ‘the shortage of tenured positions in Australian universities, the pressures experienced by all universities...and [the] appallingly low success rate in our national competitive research grant funding schemes all serve to dissuade women (and many very capable men) from choosing an academic career’ (R13). It was suggested that women are more affected by

rejection than males, and that they lack confidence to re-apply or re-submit. The longer time women commonly take to reach the same position as men is concerning to many women: 'it has taken me longer to get to the same point that a male might have reached 10 years ago...The committee might judge that I am now too old to have much of a career ahead of me although this is not really so' (R12).

The importance of international linkages and experience was emphasised. An 'overseas post-doc (1 or more) [is] very important for developing international collaborations, and getting international referees' (R6). Similarly, 'getting to international meetings and presenting your work can open up opportunities'. Overseas study leave/sabbatical is very useful if the place is 'carefully selected'. All these things, however, 'can be hard with family commitments' (R6). Many female academics with families 'expend great emotional energy juggling work/family', while men 'breeze along with their careers'.

Discussion

This study confirms the outcomes of several previous surveys of women in Australia's universities such as those by Deane et al (1996 and 1999), Devos and McLean (2000), Devos et al (2003) and Probert (2005). The performance required of senior women prevents them from reflecting often on their condition, and many of the matters that make their life less than optimal build up incrementally. They are often unaware that their frustrations are not isolated, and they do not know how to improve the situation for themselves or for their successors. We can ill-afford to ignore the perspectives that women can offer to science (Wertheim 1995: Chapter 10).

It appears, in the view of senior women in science in Australia's university system, that the number of female PhD students and lower-level employees has little bearing on the numbers of women in the professoriate. No systematic difference between type of university emerged from this small sample. The low numbers of women at associate professor level and above is due entirely, it seems, to the inability of women to develop and maintain a suitable research and publication record. This is attributed mainly to a lack of time: due to a high level of commitment to within-university activities, and a high burden of family responsibilities. The lifestyle required to gain the appropriate qualifications for success in academia is such that many talented females leave the system. The interruptions, late career starts, and lack of ability to engage in after hours and weekend work, together with lack of disposable income and physical mobility, limit the international linkages a woman can develop and maintain. This starts at the post-doctoral level, and continues throughout the career, and is compounding.

The great majority of the women surveyed consider there to be an inhibitory male culture. This is reflected in the benchmarks set for publication rates, research, and promotion, which depend on output rates that are set by men, and a lack of definition of 'relative to opportunity'. Academia has traditionally rewarded the single-minded, selfish, and supremely confident performer (how many times have we listened to someone lauded as an 'expert' and known it was mostly bluff). The 'male culture' is particularly evident in non-formal situations, where male competitiveness, aggression, lack of inclusiveness, and lack of skill recognition can often disenfranchise and disempower people (not always just women). When many 'successful' men choose life partners who have subsumed their ambition for theirs, or

are non-competitive by nature, what does this say about their reference points for women, and men's understanding of the academic woman's expectations and capabilities?

There did appear to be some variation according to discipline. 'Bench-top' science disciplines such as chemistry and biochemistry and their extensions appeared the best from a female perspective. Disciplines in which there was a strong physical component (environmental science, engineering, forestry and one would hypothesise agriculture) appeared to be particularly difficult. With the exception of the bench-top science components, medicine was particularly male-dominated.

Women's low confidence was recognised by the majority of respondents as being of concern. Without confidence, their ability to perform effectively is greatly diminished. Management at school and department level needs to be more active in developing staff and ensuring that all staff members are using their time to the best of their ability, not using some staff as a sacrificial backup for selected (usually male) 'stars'.

Practical instruments that might assist women to perform were greeted with the most enthusiasm but with caution. Study leave, and support for conference attendance, publication, and grant submission were uniformly recognised as vital and worthy of enhancement. The fear of being regarded as a 'second class citizen', however, was strong. Some internal university initiatives were regarded highly but were not universally known or appropriate. Mentoring and collegiate activities that related to 'core business' were favoured. The smaller the university, however, the fewer the opportunities for effective mentoring.

The cohort of women surveyed was by definition successful, yet many expressed feelings of frustration, exhaustion, and of disenfranchisement. Even if they felt positive, the statistics gave the lie to their situation. If the lack of visible, successful women continues, many of the advancements made at lower levels will be negated and the trends reversed. The core impediment to the future advancement of women was seen as being embedded in the benchmarks applied for seniority, and although all accepted them, they wondered whether they were appropriately applied, or indeed, appropriate. If women of intelligence are to reproduce as well as contribute to the best of their ability and talent, they need a change in societal attitudes towards them, which needs to flow on to the university system. Otherwise a return to the monastic university system seems in order. This at least will remove the 'handmaiden' wives and make the playing field more level.

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References

Commonwealth of Australia (2005) *Australian Research Council Annual Report 2004-5*, Department of Education, Science and Training, Canberra.

- Deane, E, Johnson, L, Jones, G, Lengkeek, N (1996) *Women, research and research productivity in the post-1987 universities: opportunities and constraints*. 96/21, Evaluations and Investigations Program. Higher Education Division, Department of Education, Training and Youth Affairs, Canberra.
- Deane, E, Jones, G, Lengkeek, N, Warton, A (1999) 'Does an academic appointment kill off research? A pilot study in the biological sciences,' *Journal of the Australasian Association for Institutional Research*, vol 8, no 2, 10 pp.
- Department of Education, Science and Training (2003) *Selected Higher Education Staff Statistics*, Higher Education Series. http://www.dest.gov.au/sectors/higher_education/
- Department of Education, Science and Training (2004) *Students: Selected Higher Education Statistics*, http://www.dest.gov.au/sectors/higher_education/
- Devos, A. and McLean, J. (2000) 'Let a thousand flowers bloom': women, research and the (ongoing) struggle for systemic change.' Paper presented at the Australian Association for Research in Education Conference Sydney 4-7 December 2000.
- Devos, A M, McLean, J and O'Hara, P (2003) 'The potential of women's programs to generate institutional change', *Research and Development in Higher Education* vol 26, pp.143-51
- Fox, C. (2005) *UK assets: 6,500 plus UK scientists can't be wrong*, The Athena Surveys. www.athenaproject.org.uk.
- Gardner, M. (1998) Women in Australian Universities: findings from recent research and policy implications. Presentation to the Australian Vice Chancellors' Committee. 9 pp.
- Handlesman, J, Cantor, N, Carnes, M, Denton, D, Fine, E, Grosz, B, Hinshaw, V, Marrett, C, Rosser, S, Shalala, D and Sheridan, J (2005) 'More women in science' *Science*, vol 309, no 5738, pp 1190-91.
- Hawkins, R. (2002) *The experiences of young women in science*, www.thefword.org.uk/features/2002/11 (reviewed December 2005)
- James, R, Baldwin, G, Coates, H, Krause, K-L, and McInnis, C (2004) *Analysis of equity groups in higher education*. Department of Education, Science and Training, Canberra.
- Jones, E, Urban, M, Stevenson, S, Maclachlan, M and Karmel, T (1999) *University Staff 1989 to 1998*, Higher Education Series Report No. 35, Higher Education Division, Department of Education, Training and Youth Affairs, Canberra.
- Probert, B. (2005) 'I just couldn't fit it in': gender and unequal outcomes in academic careers.' *Gender, Work and Organisation*, vol 12, no 1, pp 50-72.
- Sullivan, M (1999) 'The status of women in Australian universities: myths and realities.' *Australian Feminist Studies*, vol. 14, no 30, pp 427-33.
- Tharenou, P (1994) 'Why so few female senior academics?' *Australian Journal of Management*, vol 19, no 2, pp 221-8.
- Wertheim, M (1995) *Pythagoras' Trousers: god, physics and the gender wars*. Random House, New York.
- Winchester, H, Chesterman, C, Lorenzo, S, and Browning, L (2005) *The Great Barrier Myth: an investigation of promotions policy and practice in Australian universities*, National Colloquium of Senior Women Executives in Higher Education, Australian Vice Chancellors' Committee. University of South Australia.